

Supplemental Information

Disease Understanding and Visualization of Drug Repurposing Hypotheses

Authors

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Abstract

The increasing availability of biomedical data has opened new opportunities to rethink how diseases are modeled and how drug repurposing hypotheses can be systematically generated. In this context, we present a web-based platform that (i) provides access to previously integrated heterogeneous biomedical data and (ii) enables interactive visualization of disease understanding relationships, as well as of drug repurposing hypotheses. The platform constructs multilayer disease networks, visualizes disease relationships, and implements six complementary computational repurposing methods, including more naive methods, network-based analysis, and artificial intelligence-based approaches. It also provides the web services needed to access the whole set of data. This paper describes the underlying data sources and methodologies and demonstrates its capabilities through a representative visualization case.

Keywords

Drug Repurposing, Disease Understanding, Graph Neural Networks, Network Medicine, Visualization Platform

28 **S1. Introduction to the DRIVE platform**

29 Drug repurposing (the identification of new therapeutic applications for existing drugs)
30 has emerged as a promising approach to accelerate drug development while mitigating
31 associated risks and costs [1]. Its effective implementation relies on computational
32 platforms capable of integrating heterogeneous biomedical data and generating testable
33 hypotheses. In this context, the Medical Data Analytics Laboratory (MEDAL), based at
34 the Centro de Tecnología Biomédica (CTB) of the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid,
35 has developed the DRIVE platform (<https://drive-project.com/>).

36 DRIVE (short for Data-dRiven platform for disease Visualization and drug rEpurposing)
37 tackles these challenges by integrating multi-layered biomedical knowledge with a suite
38 of complementary computational models. The platform enables the exploration and
39 visualization of disease-related relationships and supports the systematic generation of
40 drug repurposing hypotheses. As such, DRIVE serves as a valuable resource for
41 academic researchers, clinical practitioners, and pharmaceutical stakeholders.

42 **Supplemental Figure 1** displays the landing page when accessing the DRIVE platform.
43 The navigator is formed of 5 tabs: “VISUALIZE DATA”, “TECHNICAL RESOURCES”,
44 “ABOUT”, “CONTACT” and “LOGIN/SIGN UP”. The main functionalities of DRIVE can
45 be found at the “VISUALIZE DATA” section.

46

47

Supplemental Figure 1. DRIVE platform landing page.

48 DRIVE platform includes relevant information around diseases. It is both a database of
49 disease-related information (including phenotypic, biologic and pharmacologic disease
50 features) derived from the DISNET knowledge base, as well as a platform for drug
51 repurposing. Users can obtain different visualizations of the data in the “VISUALIZE

52 DATA” section, corresponding to both the “DISEASE UNDERSTANDING” part (with
53 visualizations for disease relationships as different levels of biomedical and related
54 information, including searches by diseases and by symptoms) and to the “DRUG
55 REPURPOSING” part (with visualizations for the repurposing generated hypotheses). In
56 the “TECHNICAL RESOURCES” section, users can obtain more detailed information on
57 how we have generated the different databases that populate DRIVE platform and that
58 allow displaying the previously mentioned visualizations.

59 S2. The DISNET knowledge base

60 For DRIVE project, we envision disease understanding as a result of obtaining,
61 organizing and integrating biomedical knowledge around a central entity: disease.
62 Throughout the years, we have collected a set of publicly available, structured and
63 unstructured data related to the list of existing diseases nowadays to compile it in one
64 place: the DISNET knowledge base. DISNET (<https://disnet.ctb.upm.es/>) was a research
65 project originally executed to build a platform that enabled researchers the creation of
66 complex multilayer networks following the concepts of the Human Disease Network [2],
67 with the final purpose of generating new drug repurposing hypotheses. During its
68 execution, DISNET put together in an accessible knowledge base heterogeneous
69 information that includes large-scale biomedical data obtained and integrated from both
70 structured and unstructured sources.

71 This database constitutes a relational database that can be easily converted into a
72 heterogeneous graph. As simplified in **Supplemental Figure 2**, we organize the
73 information in 3 topological levels: the phenotypic, the biologic and the pharmacologic.
74 These 3 layers are modelled as 3 different schemas and each of them contains varied
75 disease-related characteristics. Diseases are identified by the Concept Unique Identifiers
76 (CUIs) from the Unified Medical Language System (UMLS), with the exception of the
77 phenotypic layer, where diseases have their own DISNET identifier. However, they can
78 be easily mapped and converted to CUIs.

79
80 **Supplemental Figure 2.** Schematic representation of the layers in the DISNET knowledge base [3].

81 In summary, each of the 3 layers contains the following information:

82 • **Phenotypic layer**

83 It contains information of the symptoms associated with each disease. We obtained
84 these data by mining textual data from public sources as Wikipedia, PubMed or
85 MayoClinic. The mining process includes the application of tools such as MetaMap [4],
86 a Natural Language Processing (NLP) tool that extracts UMLS medical concepts from
87 texts, and which allows us to identify symptoms and phenotypical entities in these textual
88 data. The extraction process was previously described [5].

89 • **Biologic layer**

90 It intends to represent the molecular complexity that underlies diseases. We store the
91 relationships between diseases and other entities. Namely, these entities are genes,
92 proteins, genetic variants, biological pathways, non-coding RNAs, markers, organisms,
93 and specific information related to orphan diseases. The stored relationships between
94 these entities are disease-gene, gene-protein, protein-protein, disease-variant, gene-
95 variant, gene-pathway, disease-ncRNA, and disease-marker. The information integrated
96 in this layer comes from well-known databases maintained by the scientific community
97 as DisGeNET [6], NeXtProt [7], WikiPathways [8], or MarkerDB [9], among others.

98 • **Pharmacologic layer**

99 It gathers information related to drugs. It includes relevant drug features (i.e., their
100 different codifications or structural data), as well as other associated data. Namely, the
101 targets to which the drugs bind, the diseases they treat or the phenotypical effects they
102 either are indicated for, either the ones they side-cause. Drug-drug interactions, as well
103 as the phenotypes they may be related to, are also present in the DISNET knowledge
104 base. These data were obtained and integrated from scientifically-driven and maintained
105 resources as DrugBank [10] and the Comparative Toxicogenomics Database (CTD) [11],
106 among others.

107 **S3. Computational drug repurposing methodologies**

108 Building upon the data integrated in the DISNET knowledge base, we implemented a set
109 of computational approaches with the aim of generating drug repurposing hypotheses.
110 Drug repurposing is the process of finding new therapeutic uses for already existing
111 drugs and compounds. That is, imagine there is one drug, let's call it "drug A", which has
112 been originally developed to treat a particular pathology, let's call it "original disease".
113 What drug repurposing seeks is to find other diseases different from this original disease,
114 towards which drug A is also effective. This way, drug A, which was originally developed
115 for the original disease, may be repurposed for the new disease.

116 Even though sometimes used as synonyms, strictly speaking, drug repurposing differs
117 from drug repurposing in that the former refers to drugs that have not make it to the
118 market. There are plenty of cases described in the literature that have been successful
119 in this repurposing task.

120 We have put forward a set of methodologies with the final aim of generating drug
121 repurposing hypotheses. Each methodology receives as input either a disease, either a
122 drug, either a disease-drug pair. This way, researchers may enter i) a disease, to look
123 for drugs that could be repurposed towards this disease; ii) a drug, to look for diseases
124 to which the drug can be repurposed; and iii) a disease-drug pair to understand the
125 potential of this hypothesis.

126 These methodologies share that all are computational but have different scientific
127 foundations and parameters, as it will be explained here. DRIVE platform implements a
128 set of 6 different categories of data-driven/computational repurposing methodologies,
129 including more naïve-based ones (as the corresponding for information paths and
130 threshold values), as well as network-driven (network-based proximity) and Artificial
131 Intelligence-based (Graph Neural Networks) ones.

132 • **Information paths**

133 This methodology, which was initially presented in [12] and represented in
134 **Supplemental Figure 3**, was originally developed in the context of COVID-19. Five
135 information paths were proposed, starting from COVID-associated symptoms and
136 genes. Among them, four have been implemented in the DRIVE platform, while the third
137 was excluded due to its generation of unspecific results.

138

139 **Supplemental Figure 3.** Repurposing methodology with information paths. Adapted from [12].

140 The 5 information paths are as follows:

141 → First path: The symptoms of COVID-19 were first identified, followed by the selection
 142 of drugs specifically indicated for treating those symptoms.

143 → Second path: COVID-19 symptoms were identified, followed by the extraction of
 144 diseases associated with those symptoms, and finally, the selection of drugs to
 145 treat those diseases.

146 → Third path (not included in DRIVE platform given its unspecific outcomes): COVID-19
 147 symptoms were identified, followed by the identification of diseases sharing common
 148 symptoms with COVID-19. Genes associated with these diseases were then extracted,
 149 after which the targets linked to those genes were identified, and, finally, drugs related
 150 to those targets were determined.

151 → Fourth path: Genes associated with COVID-19 were identified, followed by the
 152 extraction of diseases sharing common gene associations with COVID-19. Drugs
 153 indicated for those diseases were then identified.

154 → Fifth path: COVID-19-associated genes were identified, followed by the extraction of
 155 proteins linked to these genes. These proteins were then considered as drug targets,
 156 and the drugs associated with these targets were obtained.

157 • **Threshold values**

158 This methodology was originally presented in [13] for evaluating potential drug
 159 repurposing cases, based on disease-gene and disease-phenotype associations.
 160 DisGeNET scores were used to assess and assign weights to disease-gene associations

161 (GDAs). These scores, ranging from 0 to 1, reflect the strength of an association based
162 on existing knowledge, with higher values given to associations supported by multiple
163 databases, expert-curated resources, and larger number of publications. The scores
164 were extracted for both "Original disease – Shared Target Gene" and "New disease –
165 Shared Target Gene" associations in drug repurposing cases involving shared target
166 genes. Significant differences were identified between repurposing and non-repurposing
167 cases as reflected in **Supplemental Figure 4**. This approach generated a threshold
168 value that provides insights into which cases should be prioritized.

169

170 **Supplemental Figure 4.** Gene-disease association scores differences between repurposing cases
171 (original, in red, and new, in green, diseases) and non-repurposing cases (in blue). Adapted from [13].

172 • **Pathways**

173 Most successful drug repurposing cases adhere to the classical paradigm of "one drug,
174 one target, one disease". We explored the potential of biological pathways as key
175 elements for achieving effective drug repurposing. As a result, we identified a set of drug
176 repurposing cases, referred to as DREBIOP (Drug REpurposing based on BIOlogical
177 Pathways), which underscore the important role of biological pathways in the
178 repurposing of therapeutic agents. There are two ways of associating diseases to
179 biological pathways: direct associations reported in WikiPathways, and associations via
180 genes. This methodology was initially reported in [14] and the ideas underlying it are
181 displayed in **Supplemental Figure 5**.

182

183 **Supplemental Figure 5.** Repurposing approach following the “pathways” methodology, in particular, with
 184 the direct association between the disease and the pathway. Adapted from [14].

185 • **Disease pathways**

186 Related with the previous methodology, an additional method called disease pathways
 187 was proposed in [15]. This approach involves identifying new drug repurposing
 188 opportunities by examining the relationship between two diseases through their shared
 189 biological pathways (**Supplemental Figure 6**). It is hypothesized that when two diseases
 190 share at least one biological pathway, therapeutic drugs used for one disease may
 191 become potential candidates for the treatment of the other disease.

192

193 **Supplemental Figure 6.** Repurposing methodology with “disease pathways” approach. Adapted from [15].

194 • **Graph Neural Networks (GNNs)**

195 Several GNN models have been designed for link prediction to generate repositioning
196 hypotheses connecting disease nodes and drug nodes as represented in **Supplemental**
197 **Figure 7**. These models employ different architectures and integrate various data
198 sources to embed node vector representations and then decode their pairwise distances
199 to address the link prediction problem.

200

201 **Supplemental Figure 7.** Methodology followed to implement Graph Neural Network (GNN)-based
202 repurposing link prediction models. Adapted from [16].

203 The models are trained with a simple, reduced version of the DISNET knowledge graph,
204 as well as with the complete DISNET knowledge graph, called the complex graph. We
205 have generated 3 different versions of the GNN models, each of them outputting a score
206 ranging from 0 to 1 for each possible disease-drug pair:

207 → REDIRECTION: A model designed to predict drug-disease relationships by leveraging
208 link prediction techniques within a simple graph framework, aimed at generating drug
209 repurposing hypotheses [17].

210 → DMSR: An extension of REDIRECTION that incorporates drug molecular structures
211 as initial features for drug nodes, using GNNs to enhance the model's predictive
212 accuracy for drug repurposing [18].

213 → BEHOR: An advanced version of REDIRECTION that optimizes hyperparameters and
214 incorporates bidirectional edges to improve the prediction of drug repurposing
215 opportunities [19].

216 • **Network-based proximity**

217 Network-based proximity refers to the measurement of the relationship between entities,
218 such as diseases, drugs, and proteins, within a complex interaction network. In this
219 context, the disease-drug distances were calculated using a Z-score, which compares
220 the observed distance between a disease and a drug to a set of randomly generated
221 protein pairs, typically generated a thousand times. This metric quantifies the strength of
222 the relationship based on the network structure of protein interactions [20].

223 Network-based proximity helps to uncover how closely related the proteins associated
224 with a disease are to those linked with a drug. The closer these proteins are in the
225 network, the stronger the potential for the drug to interact with the disease, as
226 represented in **Supplemental Figure 8**. By leveraging this approach, network-based
227 proximity plays a crucial role in identifying novel drug repurposing opportunities and
228 understanding the therapeutic potential of drugs in the context of specific diseases.

229

230 **Supplemental Figure 8.** Disease-drug network proximity in the interactome to identify novel repurposing
231 opportunities.

232 S4. The DRIVE relational database

233 The DRIVE platform is supported by a relational MySQL database designed to organize,
234 store, and interconnect all the information with the systematically generated drug
235 repurposing hypotheses. The database integrates the results produced by the
236 computational methods described in Section S3, as well as their links to the underlying
237 biomedical knowledge extracted from the DISNET knowledge base. The schema of the
238 DRIVE relational database is depicted in **Supplemental Figure 9**.

239
240 **Supplemental Figure 9.** The MySQL version of the diagram of tables of the DRIVE database schema.

241 The DRIVE database structure of tables has two main components:

- 242 • Reference and entity tables, which define the fundamental biomedical entities,
243 including principally diseases and drugs. These tables store standardized
244 identifiers (e.g., UMLS CUIs for diseases, ChEMBL IDs for drugs) and provide a
245 unified reference framework for linking to the data in the DISNET knowledge
246 base.
- 247 • Generated repurposing hypotheses tables, which record the repurposing
248 predictions produced by each computational approach implemented in DRIVE.
249 Each methodology is stored in a different table (the ones starting with “dr_”
250 with their different scores (when possible) and parameters.

251 The relational design ensures data consistency and flexibility for querying complex
252 relationships among diseases, drugs, and molecular entities. It enables the automatic
253 integration of new hypotheses derived from additional computational pipelines while
254 maintaining traceability between each prediction and its biological rationale. The
255 database is implemented in MySQL Server 8.0, with foreign key constraints enforcing
256 referential integrity among entities. This structure facilitates exporting subsets of data
257 into graph-based formats for advanced analyses.

258 **S5. A use case: visualizing Colorectal Carcinoma-related**
259 **disease data and repurposing hypotheses**

260 We include a representative example to illustrate the main functionalities of the DRIVE
261 platform. The disease under study for this use case is Colorectal Carcinoma (UMLS CUI:
262 C0009402).

263 • **Disease understanding – Search by the disease (including just one disease)**

264 When the user searches for a single disease, DRIVE provides an overview of the
265 biomedical information available for that disease across the DISNET knowledge base
266 information described in Section S2: drugs, genes, pathways, proteins and symptoms.
267 **Supplemental Figure 10** shows this search for Colorectal Carcinoma related symptoms.

268
269 **Supplemental Figure 10.** DRIVE search and output for Colorectal Carcinoma symptoms in the “Visualize
270 Data > Disease Understanding > Search by Diseases > Symptoms” section.

271 • **Disease understanding – Search by the disease (including multiple diseases)**

272 When two diseases are selected, DRIVE compares and visualizes their shared and
273 distinct biomedical features. The resulting graph highlights overlapping entities such as
274 common symptoms, genes, or pathways (as shown in **Supplemental Figure 11** for the
275 case of Colorectal Carcinoma and Schizophrenia shared biological pathways)-

276
277 **Supplemental Figure 11.** DRIVE search and output for Colorectal Carcinoma and Schizophrenia shared
278 pathways in the “Visualize Data > Disease Understanding > Search by Diseases > Pathways” section.

279 • **Drug repurposing – Search by one repurposing methodology**

280 In the “Drug Repurposing” section, DRIVE integrates the output from the computational
281 methods described in Section S3 to display predicted drug-disease associations. When
282 selecting a single methodology, users can choose among the implemented
283 computational approaches to explore the repurposing hypotheses generated by each
284 model. As shown in **Supplemental Figure 12**, the user selects Colorectal Carcinoma as
285 the query disease and applies the REDIRECTION model within the GNNs methods. The
286 system outputs a ranked set of drugs predicted to have potential therapeutic activity
287 against Colorectal Carcinoma. Each result is accompanied by its associated prediction
288 score, which can be also used to filter the results.

289
290 **Supplemental Figure 12.** DRIVE search and output for Colorectal Carcinoma “Visualize Data > Drug
291 Repurposing > GNNs” section.

292 • **Drug repurposing – Multi Search functionality**

293 The Multi Search functionality enables users to simultaneously apply multiple
294 repurposing methodologies and compare their predictions in a unified view. For the
295 Colorectal Carcinoma example, the user can combine methodologies such as GNNs,
296 pathways, threshold values, information paths, and network proximity, as illustrated in
297 **Supplemental Figure 13**. This module aggregates the results from all selected methods
298 and visualizes them as an integrated network, where diseases and drugs are color-coded
299 according to the methodology that generated each association. This comparative
300 visualization helps identify robust hypotheses (i.e., drug-disease pairs predicted by
301 multiple independent methods) and provides a direct overview of the methodological
302 overlap and complementarity among DRIVE’s computational approaches.

303

304

305

Supplemental Figure 13. DRIVE search and output for Colorectal Carcinoma “Visualize Data > Drug Repurposing > Multi Search” section.

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313 **Declarations of Competing interests**

314 The authors declare no competing interests.

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